

THE POWER OF PEDAGOGICAL PERSONA: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF TEACHER PERSONALITY ON EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING

Dr. Michael Marttinson Boakye

Senior Lecturer, J. S. Addo School of Business, Marshalls University College, Ghana

Cite This Article: Dr. Michael Marttinson Boakye, “The Power of Pedagogical Persona: Exploring the Impact of Teacher Personality on Effective Teaching and Learning”, *International Journal of Computational Research and Development, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal*, Volume 9, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 9-12, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Teachers and facilitators play a very critical role in shaping the lives of their students. While their knowledge and expertise are very much essential; the impact of a teacher's personality on teaching and learning should not be underestimated. Research has shown that a teacher's personality traits can significantly influence students' motivation, engagement, and overall academic success. This paper highlights the four coordinate of a teachers' personality that influence what goes on in the classroom and the desire behavior expected to enhance inclusivity and diversity in the classroom and the school setting at large.

Introduction:

Knowledge of teaching methods, subject matter, effective teaching competency and attitude, full understanding of human growth and children development, effective communication skills, high ethical standards and ability to pursue continuing education is what constitutes an excellent teacher (Hammond and Cobb, 1995). The teachers' personality cannot be ignored in the teaching and learning process. The make up or personality influences the teaching and learning process one way or the other. Personality in this context concerns pattern of thinking, feeling and behaving evolving from biological and environmental factors. The teacher's personality reveals the thinking, feeling and the behavior of the facilitator in relation to how teaching and learning become inclusive.

Personality of the Teacher or Facilitator:

According to Cherry (2023) Personality consists the unique patterns of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that distinguishes an individual from others. Personality of an individual is based on the environmental and biological elements encountered and this remain so throughout a person's life. It is therefore, has everything to do with an individual's organised way of thinking (mindset); Organised way of feeling (Experience or emotions) and Organised ways of behavior (Activity or response to stimuli)

These three fruits of personality is determined by the teachers Biological and Environmental factors. The biological and environmental factors inform the way a teacher thinks, feels, and behaves. Sutton (2017) highlights that the thinking, feeling and behavioral processes can influence effective teaching and learning process.

The Four Coordinates of Teachers' Personality:

The effective teacher or facilitator must have the four coordinates and two by products in order to make teaching worthwhile as indicated in the figure below.

Figure 1: Coordinates of Teachers Personality

The Figure above illustrates the teachers' personality model for influencing effective teaching and learning. The teachers' knowledge about effective teaching and learning process gives birth to professional competence. Personal leadership of the teacher informs the traits evident in the teaching and the learning

process. The personal leadership gives birth to human relations technique of the teacher and traits underpins appearance.

Knowledge:

Hattie (2012) share that Knowledge is crucial in education and training of children and therefore the teacher must be knowledgeable and have something to offer. The teacher must be abreast of the three levels of knowledge attainment consisting adopted knowledge, adapted knowledge and constructed knowledge.

Adopted knowledge is information and facts learnt from others in their original form. Adapted knowledge is information and facts learnt from others but changes are made for better clarity. Constructed knowledge are the information and facts discovered through critical analysis and understanding of a subject matter. This knowledge may seem to be new knowledge added to existing ones. This is done by the process of comparing, contrasting and critiquing of facts to identify gap in knowledge and that gap becomes the new knowledge. The teacher must make teaching/learning effective by helping learners swim at all the three (3) levels of knowledge; influencing the learner with teachers' personality.

For the teacher to influence the learner with his knowledge, teacher must possess four (4) key skills. Skills with people, Skills with ideas, Skills with things/materials, skills for effective communication. Knowledge give skills.

The people skills is very necessary because you are dealing with people and the people need to be understood, loved, cared for, trained, made happy etc. The skills with ideas are needed because you must know how to deal with the people. The skills with things and materials are very important because you need them to support make your ideas clear to your learners. The effective communication skill is necessary because your ideas and materials must get to the learner for clear understanding.

The teacher must ensure that these four (4) key skills are transferred to learners because it is necessary entirely for successful life. Napoleon Hill remarks "self-confidence results first from exact knowledge and second, the ability to impact that knowledge"

Professional Competence:

Teachers with professional competency are able to adopt different teaching methods under various circumstances, interact with students within creative teaching activities. This personality is achieved through a Developed self-concept, integrated cognition, affection, perception and intuition

Developed Self-Concept:

This covers who the teacher is based on his beliefs in relation to self-scheme, past self, present self and possible or future self. A developed self-concept empowers competence and this can influence effective teaching and learning.

Integrated Cognition:

The effective teacher must combine knowledge and understanding of the knowledge. This is done through: Thought or thinking processes concerning ideas or subject matter; Experience –or encounter with subject matter and Senses or coordinating all the necessary senses for a clear understanding of a subject matter and that is necessary for intelligence. This creates meaning from reality.

Perception:

The teachers' professional competence level determines the way he perceive people, ideas and materials. Perception influences the teachers' ability to regard, understand and interpret a subject matter. This personality to a very large extend influences teaching and learning process.

Affection:

The competence level of a teacher determines how he is able to affect learners and how feedback of learners affect the lesson design and delivery subsequently.

Intuition:

The professional competence of teacher gifts him with intuition and that helps the teacher to understand the teaching and learning process through conscious deep reasoning or thinking inner self direction.

Personal Leadership:

Personal or self-leaderships determines how you affect others and vice versa. The way and manner a teacher leads himself determines to a large extent his human relations (how attitude and behavior affect others and being affected). The personal leadership of a teacher influences his work in the classroom situation and that affects the way learners learn. For the teacher to lead himself, it demands a conscious delibracy or intentionality. Toinfluence the teaching and learning process effectively it demands High self-monitors, Self- organizing principle, Educational intentionality

Self-Organizing Principles:

The first ingredient needed in personal leadership in influencing the teaching and learning in the school or classroom settings is organizing principles which may be partial or comprehensive. This is necessary to avoid unnecessary intrusion of administrators, parents, religion, culture, media and propaganda. Self-organizing principle guides the teacher in terms of classroom management, Lesson preparation and design, Lesson delivery and Human relations with students, administrators, parents etc.

Example, my self-organising principle led me to discover how to redesign the content of the syllabus according to my learner needs in terms of classroom situation, learner previous competence, learner previous experience, learner current state, school environmental factors etc. My self-organising principle led to the four (4) lesson quadrant.

Figure 2: Lesson Planning Quadrants

High Self-Monitors:

Self-monitoring is very crucial in leading oneself because it helps to monitor and control ones expressive behavior. To monitor and control expressive behavior the teacher needs two key pointers: Idiosyncratic credit pointers and idiosyncratic debit pointers.

The idiosyncratic credits are the unusual habits that are expressive to attract respect, trust, fairness, obedience among others for the teacher. This idiosyncratic credit increases the integrity of the teacher before learners, school administrator and other stakeholders. This is a powerful key to influencing effective learning as teachers have a well-developed trust, obedience and integrity with learners.

The idiosyncratic debits are unusual behavior that is expressive and likely to cause the teacher to loose good reputation, goodwill, integrity, trust among others on the side of learners and other stakeholders in education and that makes teaching and learning ineffective as the odd 2 expressive behaviors place the teacher's influence in jeopardy. Therefore the teacher must know what makes him gain credits (respect, trust, obedience, integrity) from learners and possible expressive behaviors likely to jeopardize the idiosyncratic credits

Educational Delibracy or Intentionality:

Wubbels et al. (2016) assert that teaching is an intentional activity and therefore, the teacher must be professionally intentional. This helps to influence learners for effective work. The teacher must personally lead himself through:

- Information: Knowledge acquisition
- Transformation: Knowledge application for development
- Goal setting: Specific on learning goals or on what to achieve
- Assessment: Measuring achievement to create a true picture of level of progress possibly true
- Setting new direction or theorizing - better ways out or ideas possibly true or real for better learning

The idea here is that if the teacher has knowledge through information and transformed by the possessed knowledge, that alone impacts on the way learners learn. Again, correct measuring of learning by the teacher helps him to identify better ways of learning.

Character Traits:

Trait is a distinguishing quality and character traits are the valued aspects of a person's behavior, so teachers must have a behavior valued by learners which are expressive enough to influence effective learning.

Though many scholars posit that confidence, humor, sensitivity, love, respects among others are character traits needed by the teacher. I hold the view that these necessary character traits emerges from: Professional literacy, Emotional stability, Maturity

Professional literacy produces experience, competence, knowledge, skills of pedagogy, skills with ideas, people and things for the facilitator.

Emotional stability assures a state of mind which strongly contributes directly to living a good life and happiness because emotional stability averts jealousy, stress, depression etc. Emotional stability produces alertness, joy, confidence, emotional maturity, affection, stabilized moods, humor, etc.

Maturity is the ability to respond to environmental changes appropriately covering the awareness of correct time and location to behave. This informs the teachers teaching methods, lesson design, lesson delivery, classroom managements, human relations, openness to new idea, sensitivity to others, patience, empathy, provide a free and orderly environment etc

Conclusion:

The personality of a teacher is vital in promoting teaching and learning effectively therefore keen attention must be given to that. The personality of a teacher significantly influences teaching and learning outcomes. Teachers who possess warmth, approachability, enthusiasm, empathy, emotional intelligence, and flexibility are able to enhance an environment that fosters motivation, engagement, and academic success. Jang (2019) indicates that if teachers are able to establish positive relationships with their students, it empowers students to reach their full potential. As educators, it is very necessary to note that, our personalities have effects on our classrooms and therefore we must strive to cultivate positive traits that enhance the teaching and learning experience.

References:

1. Jang, H., & Choi, H. J. (2019). The impact of teachers' personality on students' motivation and achievement. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 20(1), 27-37.
2. Wubbels, T., Brekelmans, M., den Brok, P., Levy, J., & Mainhard, T. (2016). Teacher enthusiasm: Reviewing and redefining a complex construct. *Educational Psychology Review*, 28(4), 743-769.
3. Sutton, R. E., Mudrey-Camino, R., & Knight, C. C. (2017). Teacher empathic understanding and response in relation to student personality and externalizing behaviors. *Journal of School Psychology*, 63, 33-49.
4. Hattie, J. (2012). *Visible learning for teachers: Maximizing impact on learning*. Routledge.
5. Cherry, K. (2023). *How Personality Impacts Our Daily Lives*. Personality Psychology. Very well Mind
6. Darling-Hammond, L., Bullmaster, M. L., & Cobb, V. L. (1995). Rethinking teacher leadership through professional development schools. *The Elementary School Journal*, 96, 87-106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/461816>